

Extraction of Fibres from Aerial Roots of *Giloyi* (*Tinospora cordifolia*) Tree- Finding Sustainable Sources for Bioactive Textiles

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Abstract:

Presently most research initiatives are oriented toward environmentally sustainable solutions. It is vital to address environmental challenges and eliminate non-renewable items as soon as possible. *Tinospora cordifolia* (*Giloyi tree*) is widely used in traditional Ayurvedic medicine in India. This study aimed to utilize the aerial roots of *Giloyi tree* to produce natural cellulosic fibres, the unused section of the tree. It was an exploratory study to discover natural fibre that is completely biodegradable with built-in medicinal characteristics for potential use as raw material for healthcare and sanitation products.

The fibers were extracted from the aerial roots of *Giloyi tree* using various methods, including biological, chemical, and enzymes;. For fibre extraction, treatments such as water retting, sodium hydroxide, sodium carbonate, urea, and enzymes were used. The concentration, time, and temperature of the treatments were also varied and the process was optimized for each of these treatments. Different extraction methods were used to obtain the results, which were based on the simplicity of fibre separation and the yield from each method.

Keywords: Aerial roots, Hygiene products, Sustainable fibres, *Tinospora Cordifolia* (*Giloyi Tree*), Waste utilization

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1. Introduction

Today, global warming and the exhaustion of petroleum reserves have diverted the focus to natural fibres, which are inexpensive and renewable, leading to a rise in their consumption [1]. Biopolymers, like cellulose, are the fundamental building block of natural cellulosic fibres and contribute to their biodegradability and renewability [2]. Due to certain features such as biocompatibility, inexhaustibility, and amplexity in nature, lignocellulosic fibres have seen their usefulness in different domains [3]. Natural gum, which is contained in the plant strands and assists in their adhesion, must be eliminated during the retting process in order to split up the fibre strands from it. Various retting processes include dew/field [4], NaOH [5], and chelating agent EDTA [6].

One of the most economically and ecologically expensive commercial crops to produce is cotton. Cotton production has the second-largest agricultural use of pesticides in the world with five of the most dangerous pesticides used that are known to be cancer-causing apart from being environmentally dangerous. The 60 per cent of the total fibre production in the world accounts for cotton, although during the last three decades man-made fibres have made significant inroads into cotton's share. This situation is aggravated by the rising price of cultivating cotton and other natural cellulosic fibres like jute and linen [7].

Known as *Guduchi/Giloyi*, *Tinospora cordifolia* is a large, deciduous climbing shrub in the *Menispermaceae* family. China and the Indian subcontinent are the main distribution areas. *Giloyi* is the term that is widely used in Hindi for *Tinospora cordifolia*. This term has a folkloric expression that has maintained the celestial beings alive and young with the help of this divine medicine. The aerial roots of the *Giloyi* are long filamentous and extend from the stem's branches [8].

In certain ayurvedic medicines, the use of *Giloyi* has been acknowledged as one of the significant elements. Anti-spasmodic, antipyretic, anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-leprotic are some of the properties that have been discovered in the dry bark of *Giloyi* [8, 9].

This study attempted to extract natural cellulosic fibres from the aerial roots of the *Giloyi*, that has inherent antimicrobial and other medicinal properties which are an added advantage for the products made from these fibres. In designing the study, the following research goals were taken into account:

- i. Optimization of conditions for fiber extraction from aerial roots of *Tinospora cordifolia*.
- ii. Assessment of the ease of extraction of fibres under optimal conditions.
- iii. Comparison of various physical properties of fibres extracted using different methods
- iv. Measurement of the percentage yield of fibres extracted.

2. Materials and Methods

Aerial roots of *Tinospora cordifolia* (*Giloyi*) were procured from the campus of Lady Irwin College, New Delhi. Chemicals used were Sodium Hydroxide, Sodium Carbonate, Urea, Hydrogen Peroxide, EDTA, Sodium Silicate, and Bactosol CBS Liquid (procured from Archroma). All the chemicals were of laboratory reagent grade.

2.1 Extraction of Fibres

Table 1 summarises the optimal parameters used for extraction of the fibres

Table 1: Optimized Parameters Used for Extraction of Fibres

Treated with	Concentrations Used	Time Duration (min)	Temperature	MLR
Na ₂ CO ₃	5g/l & 7.5g/l	30, 60, 90 & 120	90°C	1:40
NaOH	5g/l & 7.5g/l	30, 60 & 90	60°C (5g/l) & 90°C (7.5g/l)	1:40
Urea	5%, 7.5% & 10% (owm)	30, 60, 90 & 120	90°C	1:40
Enzyme	2.5%, 5% & 7.5% (owm)	60, 120, 180 & 240	75°C (ph-7)	1:40

2.1.1 Bleaching and softener treatment of Extracted Fibres

The bleaching of extracted fibres was done using Hydrogen Peroxide to decolorize them and for their further segregation, a solution of 0.5g/l EDTA, 10g/l Sodium Silicate, 2g/l Sodium Carbonate (to maintain a pH 10-11) and 0.5% of Hydrogen peroxide (MLR 1:30) was used [10]. The fibres were then added in the solution, and bleaching was carried out for 45 minutes at 90°C. Dilute acetic acid was then used for neutralizing the treated fibres. After this polysiloxane commercial softener was used, which further increased the flexibility of fibres.

2.2 Testing of Extracted Fibres

The physical properties that were examined included length, fineness, strength and elongation by using standardized test methods. The test method numbers IS 10014 Part-1, IS 10014 Part-2 and IS 3675 were used to determine the fibre length, fibre denier, elongation and bundle strength of the extracted fibres respectively.

3. Results and Discussion

The study was conducted to examine the possibility of extracting fibres from the aerials roots of *Tinospora cordifolia* (*Giloyi*) using various chemical methods. The different extraction methods that were explored were water retting, alkaline treatment with sodium carbonate and sodium hydroxide, treatment with urea and enzymatic treatment. The extracted fibres were tested for various physical properties, ease of extraction and percentage yield to do a comparative analysis between the different methods. The results obtained have been presented under different heads in the subsequent sections.

3.1 Water Retting

At room temperature, 10 g of dried aerial roots were stored for 15, 30, 45, and 60 days (water was changed after every 7 days). The cork, which consisted of a group of fibres, was visible and swollen by the end of 45 days, making extraction easier. After the period of 45 days, the extraction of fibres was done manually (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Fibres extracted using water retting

3.2 Treatment with Sodium Carbonate

10 grams of dried aerial roots of *Giloyi* were treated with different concentrations of Na_2CO_3 with varying concentration and time.

3.2.1 Effect of concentration and time

The fibres extracted were finer when treated at 7.5g/l concentration of Sodium Carbonate than when treated at 5g/l (Table 2). With increase in time the ease of extracting the fibres also improves. The finest extraction was seen when treated with 5g/l for 60 minutes. Increasing the time to 90 minutes did not further enhance the ease of extraction. Fibre extraction after 30 minutes was easier to extract than those extracted after 60, 90, and 120 minutes of treatment with 7.5g/l Na_2CO_3 . (Table 2). The best Na_2CO_3 extraction condition was 7.5g/l Na_2CO_3 at 90°C for 60 minutes with an MLR of 1:40.

3.3 Treatment with Sodium Hydroxide

10 grams of dried aerial roots were treated each with varying concentrations of NaOH at two different temperatures for varying time duration.

3.3.1. Effect of concentration, temperature and time

Aerial roots when treated with 7.5g/l concentration at 60°C the fibres were extractable (Table 2). With time the ease of extraction increases. The best extraction with 5g/l occurred when treated for 90 minutes. Furthermore, no difference was observed. The ease of extracting the fibre improved slightly when the concentration was increased to 7.5 g/l. Individualization of fibre bundles was also achieved in 60 minutes for this concentration (Table 2). The best extraction condition for NaOH treatment was found to be a 60-minute time period with 7.5g/l NaOH at 60°C.

3.4 Treatment with Urea

10 grams of dried aerial roots of *Giloyi* were treated with varying conditions using urea.

3.4.1 Effect of concentration and time

The outer layer was not fully removed when treated with a 5% owm concentration, making extraction tough (Table 2). The outer layer of the fibres began to collapse using 7.5% owm concentration, making extraction easier. The 10% owm concentration of Urea showed the finest result (Table 2). At 5% owm with the increase in time to 60 minutes, fibres were relatively easily extracted and no difference was seen further. At 7.5% owm with time extraction was made easy. 90 minutes were found to be sufficient to bring about some individualization. No further improvement was seen.

When extracting the fibres with a 10% owm urea concentration, the fibres were extracted more easily than with prior concentrations as time went on. The best urea extraction condition was found to be a concentration of 10% owm with MLR of 1:40 at 90°C for 120 minutes (Table 2).

3.5 Enzyme Treatment

10 grams of dried aerial roots of *Giloyi* were treated with varying concentrations of Bactosol CBS Liq. (a commercial pectate lyase enzyme).

3.5.1 Effect of concentration and time

At lower concentrations, the outermost layer of the fibre was hard. At 5% owm breakdown starts, making extraction easier (Table 2). Furthermore, no difference was seen. Enzymes are more expensive than the other agents used in fibre extraction. Because raising the concentration did not result in a significant improvement in fibre separation, a lower concentration (5% owm) is preferred.

At 2.5% concentration, outer cell was hard to remove before 180 minutes, after that, it started degrading and easily extracted. Therefore, when lower concentration of enzyme is used, it is recommended to carry out the treatment for at least 2 hours before any effect on the outer epidermis layer is seen.

At 5% owm concentration, the mechanism of action of the enzyme was on pectin which has the function of adhesion. As a result of rupturing, fibres adhered inside are released. The outer cell wall of those treated for less than five minutes was difficult to dissolve because the enzyme required more time to dissolve it. After 180 minutes of treatment, the extraction process was simpler since pectin had probably disintegrated. In the case of 7.5% owm concentration, the extraction process becomes easier with time [10].

Table 2 shows that the best fibres were extracted when enzymes were used at 5% owm with 1:40 MLR at 90°C and pH 7 for 180 minutes.

Table 2: Fibres Extracted after Treatment with Various Condition and Methods

	30 minutes	60 minutes	90 minutes	120 minutes
Na₂CO₃ 5g/l				
7.5g/l				
NaOH 5g/l				
7.5g/l				
Urea 5%owm				
7.5%owm				

10%owm				
Enzyme	60 minutes	120 minutes	180 minutes	240 minutes
2.5% owm				
5% owm				
7.5% owm				

3.6 Yield of Fibres after Extraction

Fig. 2 depicts the yield percentage of fibres obtained from the aerial roots of *Giloyi* after treatment with different conditions.

Figure 2: Yield Percentage of Extracted Fibres

3.7 Bleaching using Hydrogen Peroxide

Hydrogen peroxide was used for the bleaching method. Fibre separation occurred easily and the color of the fibres also became light after bleaching treatment (Fig.3).

Figure 3: Extracted fibres after Bleaching treatment

3.8 Softening Treatment

The fibres treated using NaOH were stiff and had a harsh feel. The improvement in the luster and pliability of fibres were seen after a polysiloxane commercial softener treatment (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: Fibres extracted using NaOH bleached and given softener treatment

3.9 Analysis of Physical Properties of Extracted Fibres

Table 4 depicts the values of the different parameters of physical properties tested for the fibres extracted using various extraction methods.

Table 4: Physical properties of the fibres extracted from aerial roots of Giloyi tree

S. No.	Test Parameter	A Water Retting	B Treatment with Na ₂ CO ₃ , bleached	C Treatment with NaOH	D Treatment with NaOH, bleached	E Treatment with urea, bleached	F Treatment with enzyme, bleached
1.	Fibre length (mm)	193.77	207.97	432.23 (Longest)	274.8	254.33	293.1
2.	Fibre denier	85.01	93.45	75.08 (Finest)	91.72	89.44	96.30
3.	Bundle strength (g/tex)	7.55	13.47	16.95 (Good Strength)	13.56	13.67	13.63
4.	Elongation (%)	3.77	5.71	6.99	7.80 (Maximum)	6.22	6.12

From the results obtained for the physical properties, it was seen that fibres extracted from treatment with NaOH before bleaching yielded the longest fibre with length of 432.23mm and the shortest were the fibres extracted from the water retting with length of 193.77mm. Fibres treated with NaOH before bleaching yielded the finest fibre of all with 75.08 denier and the coarser fibre was extracted when treated using enzyme with 96.30 denier. In terms of bundle strength fibres extracted using NaOH before bleaching shows good strength of 16.95g/Tex and the lowest was seen in the fibres extracted using water retting of 7.55g/tex. Maximum amount of stretch (elongation) was obtained by NaOH after bleaching as 7.80% and the lowest stretch resulted by water retting method of 3.77%. The effect of alkali and bleaching agent seems to change the polymer orientation and makes the fibres more amorphous which helps the fibres in further elongation.

4. Conclusion

The final evaluation of the effectiveness of the extraction method was done in terms of quality of fibres extracted, ease of extraction and the overall yield from each method. In comparison, it was observed that those treated with enzyme (5% owm) concentration for 180 minutes were easiest to extract than other fibres. The fibres which were extracted from the enzyme treatment were also good in yield percentage. The fibres extracted using NaOH were the finest and longest with good bundle strength. The highest percentage of elongation was observed in fibres treated with NaOH followed by bleaching.

This being done from an unused part of the plant can be a sustainable alternative source for cellulosic fibres. With a documented list of medicinal value and properties of this plant, it can find good use in various textile applications and especially as bioactive textiles in health and hygiene products. The aerial roots of *Giloyi* used for the study were also not pulled or cut from the tree but were used when they fell from the trees on their own. This is a very effective way to conserve the environment and a good method of utilizing plant waste.

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